

PECULIARITIES OF PREPARATION OF MEDICAL DIGITAL PLATFORM “MÄHREM ENE” FOR PREGNANT WOMEN’S UTILIZATION

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The medical field has always had an interest in the incorporation of technological advances into practice [1]. Many early adopters of mobile phones sought to evaluate their impact on clinical care as a medical reference. Throughout the early twenty-first century several studies evaluated the benefits of mobile devices as a way to increase communication, improve access to the medical literature, and streamline productivity and clinical workflow [2].

Pregnancy and delivery are considered to be one of the most important experience in women’s lives, as well as an opportunity for screening their health and reinforcing healthy behaviors. As pregnant women go through various physical, psychological, and social changes, their need for information and seeking behavior often increase. While learning about healthy pregnancy, pregnant women learn that their health practices directly affect fetal health and pregnancy results [3].

Reliable source of getting this type of information definitely doctor advices. In addition, medical supervision is necessary during pregnancy and for the healthy growing up of the newborn baby.

Through using this platform, it is possible to keep track of the health of the mother and child using the potentials of the digital system.

In this software, it is possible:

- to monitor the accounts of all pregnant women and newborns registered in state, provincial, city, village polyclinics;
- to track week by week pregnancy using pregnancy calendar;
- to manage medical checkups schedules and medical records;
- reminders medical checkups;
- take notes, keep diary about pregnancy symptoms, doctor visits;
- to chat online with doctor, get information and advices about healthy eating, collect and share data with doctor;
- to track calendar of newborn;
- to monitor baby’s healthcare information.

In addition to the above-mentioned, this program includes a collection of children fairy tales, children songs and baby lullabies for them to go to sleep. In this platform has "Mahrem-Ene online shop" page, which will make a special contribution to the development of digital trade and digital economy, and the "Mahrem-Ene pharmacy" page, where the online pharmacy operates also includes.

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